

WHITE PAPER

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**EUROPEAN TECHNOLOGY
PLATFORM FOR HIGH
PERFORMANCE COMPUTING**

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Executive Summary

This White Paper is part of European Technology Platform's Strategic Research Agenda 6, outlining strategic research priorities for HPC system software and management. The white paper covers the State of the Art, Upcoming Challenges, Post Exascale Vision and Key Research and Innovation recommendations. Major focus areas include: managing increasingly heterogeneous hardware architectures, improving energy efficiency and sustainability, enhancing security measures for sensitive data processing, and developing flexible software stacks that can support diverse workload requirements. The white paper emphasizes the need for "software factories" - automated infrastructure for building and maintaining verifiable software components - and standardized federated services to enable effective resource sharing and workflow management across different computing paradigms.

Glossary of acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High Performance Computing
HPDA	High Performance Data Analytics
ML	Machine Learning
MSA	Modular Supercomputing Architecture
PMix	Process Management Interface - Exascale
RJMS	Resource and Job Management System
SSO	Single Sign-On
SRA	Strategic Research Agenda
TRL	Technical Readiness Level

Introduction

The hourglass model of layered systems architecture [1] prescribes a distinguished layer in a stack of abstractions (sometimes termed the spanning layer [2]) that serves as the sole means of accessing the lower-level resources of the system. HPC system software resides at this waist of the hourglass, representing the meeting point between applications and infrastructure, and enabling their interoperation.

System software in HPC can be subdivided in three groups:

- **Software that allows management and monitoring of the hardware and software resources on the supercomputer.** It requires (i) a comprehensive set of tools to be able to deploy and maintain whole infrastructure; (ii) an operating system (commonly Linux) distribution optimized for the underlying hardware; and (iii) a versatile and effective resource scheduling and orchestration service able to allocate resources in regard to the different application or workflow needs.
- **Software that manages application data.** From a data point of view, up to now HPC applications use POSIX files (HDF, CEPH, Lustre). However, for HPDA and AI applications, other, better suited object data organizations (such as object or key-value stores) should be supported by supercomputers.
- **Application-oriented software stack** that implements programming models and APIs as required to develop and execute HPC and AI applications/workflows on supercomputers.

System software solutions need to:

- Support the **expanding application scope and diversity**, in particular supporting the requirements of the convergence of Simulation (classic HPC), HPDA(High-Performance Data Analytics) and AI/ML processing as part of the same compute continuum.
- Master the **complexity of combinations of optimized or specialized hardware and software**, with runtime environments and tools supporting dynamic, flexible and efficient execution models.
- Offer **smart tools** to assist in the development, deployment, optimisation and control of the efficiency of applications/workflows on heterogeneous hardware architectures.
- Support **mixed generations of hardware** and their interoperability. This need will become a challenge for runtime systems, and for applications portability.

State of the Art

Power efficiency, scalability, and support for system heterogeneity still drive the system software landscape at Exascale and Post-Exascale for 2025-2030. The convergence of Simulation (HPC), HPDA and AI in the same compute continuum can be represented as the meeting point between applications and infrastructure, with increasing pressure for the spanning layer (as per the hourglass model) to remain both effective in terms of advanced functionality and efficient in terms of overheads. The combination of multiple workloads coming from AI and data analytics and conventional HPC applications on the same supercomputing infrastructure is now a reality that is reinforced by the compute needs of AI applications.

Software stack: constant evolution

Four elements will have major impacts on the system software ecosystem beyond 2025.

- **Integration of resources and applications/workflows purely related to the field of AI into supercomputers:** The support of AI (both for model training and for online inference) in multiple fields of application by powerful companies will on the one hand drive technology optimization and calibration to the potential disadvantage of classical HPC, for instance by de-emphasizing FP64 performance in future systems. On the other hand, it will strongly influence the integration choices of the components of the software stack, as AI workloads come with assumptions about the availability of popular non-HPC software stacks (eg. Pytorch, TensorFlow). There is an acute need to deal with heterogeneous architectures in the compute continuum. As an example, system software must provide flexible and easy-to-use tools, including compiler toolchains and build environments, to support multi-architecture executables, both in the already common form of fat binaries but also in the form of on-demand build and deployment capabilities.
- **RISC-V's progress:** The increasing interest in and adoption of open-standard RISC-V technologies in the fields of embedded (esp. automotive) and edge computing is undeniable. The compute continuum, which integrates metrics captured by instruments and experimental results, will therefore be impacted. Interest in RISC-V accelerators and servers is also growing, but with still relatively low levels of TRL, and diversity in the set of supported ISA extensions. Once again, this raises the problem of compatibility of software stacks. Furthermore, optimized support for languages, programming models, APIs and development tools that allows application/workflow developers to abstract themselves from this added complexity and diversity during development will become crucial.
- **Integration of quantum technologies:** Quantum computing is a very promising technology that is not today mature and will require a significant, continuous investment to reach maturity and be effectively integrated in HPC infrastructures. As the new technologies require cooperation with standard computing solutions, integration must be driven primarily by application requirements. Focusing on applications/workflows will help to identify and develop the software and related standards to effectively support the new technology. It will also provide a more accurate evaluation of the advantages in terms of time, energy or cost to solution. This complete application-focused vision is needed to guide research on future computing technologies.
- **Data and resource protection:** The workflow and the flow of data of future applications/workflows will change the way to best integrate and manage storage, network and computing resources inside and around supercomputers. Federated services for computation and data, together with corresponding Cloud-like services,

need to be integrated with software stack solutions. Their usage is different from HPC, more flexible and more volatile in terms of perimeters, requiring HPC operators to revisit the access and governance policies of supercomputer centres. Data protection is not an HPC-specific problem, but HPC needs to be able to adopt the same strategies and rules as BDVA or Cloud providers on this topic. Sharing resources with AI applications will require strong capabilities to control the future usage of trained models.

From convergence of usage to convergence of stack: an integration issue

Today, the HPC world realizes that there is more to data storage than just files and that self-service ideas i.e. minimising system administrator intervention for resource provisioning (e.g. by offering advanced policy-driven resource provisioning functionality through a HPC gateway/portal) are attractive to users. HPC communities also realize the importance of the compute continuum and the need for dynamic ingestion of data during simulations. In the meantime, the AI and big-data worlds have adopted accelerators and fast network infrastructure, just like HPC has successfully done over several generations of such hardware. All Cloud providers now offer HPC services running on HPC-class systems and currently HPC centres are looking to add Cloud-based technologies to their offerings. The convergence of HPC/HPDA/AI workloads is a major milestone in the evolution of system software infrastructure and tools. This convergence needs strong integration and validation capabilities to master the integration of this new software stack, including more interactive usage modes (e.g. user-created Jupyter notebooks). Today initial managed build and deployment environments have been put in place by Exascale computing centres; however, complete integration, fully standardized and shared best practices, across cloud, AI, and HPC are not yet fully achieved.

Mastering efficiency and cost: instrumentation and AI enhancements requirements

Power consumption and the carbon footprint of supercomputers are very high. While tools have been put in place to monitor and control power usage, the hard challenge of maximizing efficiency in the use of supercomputers remains, as it requires deep insight into applications, strong tuning expertise and use of dynamic scheduling/orchestration practices. Strong investment is needed to reliably and with minimal manual effort identify the critical parameters of an application profile and improve resource usage by the application. AI integration with performance and monitoring tools at the application and system level is expected to result in significant progress. Even with the scientific community having achieved a better understanding of the gap between hardware and software and efficient application/workflow execution, the evolution of the application-oriented software stack is still very slow (compared to the rate of changes in the computing/storage/communication infrastructure and the overall execution environment). Further investment needs to be pursued to more quickly improve application efficiency.

Tools and Services for Security Incident Detection and Response in a Scientific Ecosystem: An emerging critical need

Additional challenges continue to emerge in the security field. It is becoming more pressing to consider the exposure of supercomputers to growing security risks. The convergence of HPC/HPDA/AI workloads and the development of hybrid computing infrastructures (Cloud & supercomputer, Edge & supercomputer) and the compute continuum exposes HPC centres and systems to very serious security risks, which cannot be ignored. The compute continuum and the sharing of supercomputing resources by new types of applications are critical points for security, as they create more entry points to computing resources, beyond the currently prevalent paradigm of “perimeter defence”, and require additional access checks and verification.

The flexibility of application containers could be also a way to covertly execute non-verified and potentially malicious applications. The software stacks which run on supercomputer resources are not strictly built and maintained by supercomputer administrators anymore, but rather must become more evolvable and composable. We do not have today a process to verify through a “*software factory*” process (i.e. a tool-assisted regimented process for building software with verifiable provenance), so that a CVE (i.e. a publicly disclosed cybersecurity defect, listed in the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures database) is indeed mitigated in such fluid software stacks.

Upcoming Challenges (2025 – 2028)

Even with new hardware technology and system architectures such as RISC-V, processing-in-memory (PIM), and Quantum computing requiring significant evolution of the software stack, the main challenge will be to develop tools and practice for integration and efficient usage of such new resources by a new style of applications. The core challenges for system software remain essentially the same as in SRA5 [5], but with increased urgency in improving flexibility in the integration and efficient utilization of software components and services outside the common elements of classic HPC environments, while at the same time enhancing security measures to provide protection to both code and data.

Challenges for beyond 2026

Convergence of Simulation (HPC), HPDA and AI in the same IT continuum

Converged HPC/HPDA/AI workloads have different characteristics from pure HPC workloads and therefore require additional features on the systems they run on. With compute-intensive workloads currently running on HPC clusters, primary concerns are close-to-the-metal performance and efficient use of high-end/dedicated hardware in an environment where users are granted exclusive, albeit time-limited, access to resources. With data-intensive (HPDA, AI) workloads, currently running mostly on Cloud systems but also on HPC infrastructures, primary concerns are the instant and elastic availability of resources and fault tolerance, in a multi-tenant environment and with sufficient flexibility to select between a “self-service” operating mode or rely on a ready-made software stack. Converged systems should be able to cope with wide-ranging workload diversity and AI-inspired solutions could be used for efficiently managing the complexity introduced. It is important to be able to reconfigure data centre resources, building new virtual infrastructures out of existing building

blocks dynamically: elastic reconfiguration at runtime and efficient dynamic scheduling are potential solutions. New technologies such as AI methods and AI-optimized hardware or including observations made by commodity-devices and IoT data streaming offer new potential for scientific methodologies and workflows. Some of the toughest technical challenges will depend on understanding and modelling the data and workflows in the underlying multi-owner, and multi-tenant compute infrastructure. The data and compute continuum is a disruption for present application development putting a major emphasis on defining data-aware execution flows and ensuring security across the full application workflow.

HPC systems and particularly converged HPC/HPDA/AI systems will need to provide system software support for advanced security mechanisms to satisfy increasingly pressing requirements for trustworthy processing of sensitive datasets and reliable time-sensitive response in the case of urgent computing. This support includes assistance from the OS for putting in place several essential security mechanisms enabling isolation and verifiably trusted execution. Particular concerns arise from the need to process sensitive data sets (such as Personally Identifiable Information and data under intellectual property restrictions), necessitating protection against loss of integrity and confidentiality.

At the architecture and system levels, computing together with data concerns will drive supercomputer design. Near-memory computing, including processing-in-memory (PIM), integrated at different locations of the architecture can potentially have a great impact, and necessitates advances in system software support. Kernel-bypass networking is a promising technique to address the throughput and system stack scalability issues, but we still lack comprehensive support for standardised vendor-neutral interfaces and protocol implementations for applications to benefit from them. DPDK (Data Plane Development Kit) and SPDK

(Storage Performance Development Kit) are notable examples of hardware-assisted system software frameworks that facilitate high-performance user-mode access to networking and storage, respectively, while mostly bypassing OS kernel involvement. Programmable packet processing is an emerging technique for applications that can offload their request processing in part or in full to the NIC. OS support for resource disaggregation will offer new capabilities for applications and runtime-specific optimisations, including support for systems structured as shared pools of memory and storage resources.

Even if the operating system and hardware and smart I/O services are expected to enhance data access and data sharing, major efficiency improvements will depend on application adaptation and likely redesign to minimise data movement over the multiple steps of a computation or multiple steps of the workflow. The real challenge of convergence appears to lie in integrating flexibility with heterogeneity. System architects and application programmers need to re-think the way that information is accessed, shared and stored. A more flexible science-technology co-design flow with fast turnaround of innovation at the interface between science applications, computing systems engineering and computational science is clearly needed, and can be expedited by increased investments towards initiatives that show promise to achieve long-term technical goals as well as to contribute to the establishment and adoption of practical best practices. Adaptation can be very intrusive, influencing the way in which applications are designed and deviating from the classic first-principles-driven science and linear-workflow approach. Support capabilities such as systems for workflow and dataflow deployment and orchestration, data location and logistics and dynamic resource allocation (compute, network, storage) are complex issues that will require progressive enhancements in order to address major challenges such as security, efficiency, programmability and reproducibility. A practical challenge lies in the effective integration of all available resources and tools into the common allocation and scheduling modes of HPC.

Resource management is challenging for any computing setup. However, in a compute continuum environment [3], where edge devices, heterogeneous nodes and both cloud and HPC resources are integrated, this management involves additional difficulties. Indeed, the main challenges to face are:

- There is a lack of a global architecture of the complete environment and scheduling decisions must be done in a distributed manner.
- The wide variety of compute, storage and communication systems that take part of a compute continuum infrastructure makes efficient and secure integration and management of these resources more complex. Interoperability is also an issue for the seamless integration of HPC, AI and Cloud technologies.
- Edge devices and intermediate nodes (fog computing) are usually limited in processing and memory resources, and these limitations affect the appropriate allocation of resources to the different parts of the compute continuum infrastructure.
- It is vital to enable local computing on the edge, minimising the data movement between layers and the energy consumption as far as possible, but safeguarding an adequate quality of service level.
- Workflows should be deployed and/or migrated between different layers of the compute continuum environment, and the scheduling and orchestration systems have to map the workflows adequately in the complex infrastructure, minimising the energy used and optimising the performance.

Efficiency of the combination of HPC/HPDA/AI infrastructure and application execution environments

To minimize power consumption, the hardware will be increasingly heterogeneous, and it will use processors for computation and orchestration of the dataflows and diverse accelerators, such as FPGAs and GPUs or their derivatives for HPC computing and Deep Learning. At the global level, electricity power sizing and its associated cost ultimately limit the size of the machine: higher energy efficiency allows a more powerful system for the same cost. There are several options to increase the efficiency of the supercomputer and the centre hosting it; In practice, they should all be combined:

- “Adequate/ appropriate” computing - The idea is to adapt the accuracy of the operation to the needs. For example, the learning process in Deep Learning does not really need double-precision floating-point arithmetic operations and GPUs are directly supporting reduced-precision data types (eg. FP16, FP8, FP4, INT16, INT8, INT4), which seems to be sufficient (at least for inference processing) while decreasing the size and energy required. Some arithmetic operations do not even need to be exact, so operators can be simplified while being “good enough” for the requirements. On the other hand, floating point representations can induce errors in iterative computing and new formats (e.g. UNUM) can potentially help in containing numerical instability. A similar approach (called “model quantisation”) is being applied in the AI domain. However, uncertainty quantification needs to be considered as well, as often uncertainties are involved, arising for example from inexact measurements or modelling assumptions.
- Application specific hardware is more efficient in terms of FLOPS/Watt or Ops/Watt than the general-purpose option because computing resources are tuned to the application class and their control is more efficient. For example, in terms of throughput, GPUs are more efficient than general purpose processors, yet their compute capabilities are more limited (SIMD instead of MIMD execution) and, as a result, programming can be more difficult in the general case. Capabilities for reprogramming or dedicated software optimisation will need to be created. It will be a challenge not only from the programmer’s point of view but also from the point of view of system managers to combine different accelerators into a unified programming model supported by a dynamic and elastic resource management infrastructure. A modular architecture capable of orchestrating heterogeneous computing resources at system-level is essential to support a unified programming model [6].
- In situ/in transit processing - In situ processing is a more efficient alternative, allowing data visualisation, curation, structuring or analysis to happen online and on the simulation systems, i.e. as data is generated by the simulations, thus reducing the volume of refined data to be stored and in consequence saving energy. Big Data management approaches include in situ processing capabilities that are of particular interest for addressing this challenge, i.e. by bringing the computation to where data is located. With ever increasing emphasis on data processing in converged HPC/HPDA/AI infrastructures, there is a pressing need to improve data streaming support at the network and OS levels.
- Decarbonization is an emerging topic that puts emphasis on sustainability of hardware and software for HPC. Providers of hardware, software, or data will need to publish the carbon footprint of production, operation, and recycling for each product offering. Reuse of energy from computing waste heat can reduce the overall carbon footprint further. For that we need tools to be able to quantify and manage the carbon footprint [4], and also to rethink the life requirements, and the Carbon ROI of solutions. The slowdown in the growth of CPU clock speed, and corresponding core performance, is likely to incentivise extending the useful life of HPC system deployments. Operating multiple generations of

hardware may bring interoperability challenges, which need to be balanced with the potential savings from avoiding, or at least deferring, the effort of rewriting application codes for performance tuning.

- Data-aware system policy: Heterogeneity of computing resources and the large amount of data required by applications have a detrimental impact on the locality of data/processing capabilities. The energy cost, combined with the carbon footprint, of data movement is a great challenge that needs to be considered in the co-design of applications and in workflow orchestration.

Availability of tools for dynamic and flexible execution models

New software stack integration and compliance capabilities will be necessary to support application portability over heterogeneous infrastructures. Software-defined infrastructure solutions offer advanced policy-driven data and resource management capabilities for managing storage and compute resources respectively. The current state-of-the-art does not yet adequately cover the evolution of HPC environments towards the goal of prompt decision support [7]. Regardless of whether the computing is HPC, HPDA or AI, launching units of work (commonly called “jobs” in the HPC system context) with high resource requirements will require efficient support to reduce job launch latency, monitor job progress and resource consumption in real time, and adapt to unplanned node downtime and other failures. We need to consider the technical implications of **flexible usage modes of HPC infrastructure**, scientific modelling software, analytics and AI/ML-based applications in combination with data assets for the purposes of decision-making support. The following list discusses in detail the dynamic and flexible usage of HPC infrastructures driven by software:

- For prompt, or even urgent, decision support, the conventional usage model of HPC centres, which relies on relatively long-term arrangements to enable time-scheduled use to share resources based on well-established access policies, is not

adequate. In urgent decision support scenarios, stakeholders distinct from the conventional users of HPC centres, particularly the members of incident response teams, need to interact with HPC workflows on a demand-based basis, i.e. have the capability to initiate and control the actual processing schedule, while engaging significant HPC and data processing resources in a Cloud-like manner (both hosted in a HPC centre, but possibly at external Cloud-like sites as well) based on their real-time assessment on how a complex situation evolves over time [8].

- Applying HPC in a wide range of use-cases for **insight extraction and decision support in short timescales** brings about increased dynamicity/diversity in the definition of what is the unit-of-work to be managed, including ensembles of jobs, data-staging to support workflows, and interactions with services/facilities external to the HPC system. Model-based simulation, the real-time adaptation of interlinked computational models of evolving complex processes and distributed data-driven scientific collaborations necessitate advances towards more interactive access to HPC resources and pre-emption support, in the context of dynamic workflows over large datasets that require consideration of several challenges, with both technical and organizational aspects. Specific technical challenges arise in the following areas: dynamic resource allocation and scheduling, pre-emption techniques with fast job checkpointing and restart, coordination of resource managers, short-notice secure access to federated HPC resources, data-intensive workflow support (including data staging on node-local storage), increased interactivity (including pre-emption and simulation steering). We have outlined a set of short- to medium-term recommendations for R&D actions towards improving the effective use of HPC resources for insight extraction and decision support in short time scales.

- **Public clouds** are attractive for several use cases where users benefit by providing flexibility, scalability, pay-per-use, and removing initial investment for their HPC workloads. However, they can come with unpredictable costs, or can be hard to optimize outside of the provider's initial design intent for the increasing diversity and complexity of many domain-specific, data-intensive HPC and AI/DL workloads. On the other hand, private clouds (on-premises or off-premises delivered by a managed services provider with HPC expertise) can be highly customized with legacy integration to provide significant HPC capabilities while enabling cloud end-user experience and agility. Therefore, a trending usage mode is a shift towards hybrid HPC, leveraging cloud-based options to augment on-premises HPC capabilities, i.e. extending traditional on-premises HPC systems with flexible private cloud (off-premises) infrastructure. A data-aware governance policy is essential in such a deployment, with emphasis on data sovereignty and lifecycle, as well as controls for operational costs.
- **Matching hardware resource capabilities with applications-oriented environments** is a great challenge, requiring the evolution of multiple tools. Even if virtualisation abstractions help to deploy applications over multiple architectures, significant tools evolution will be required to address variability of resources and ensure near-optimal efficiency of resource use. Application development for this level of complex architecture will require effective programming APIs, new run time combinations and tools that offer an abstraction layer that hides a part of this complexity and guarantees application portability. Moreover, we need tools to analyse, profile, trace and predict efficiency of flexible execution environments. Embedded AI and analytics methods will be helpful to master the complexity of development and deployment of this new style of applications.

- Moreover, **AI integration in HPC/HPDA/AI application workflows** (including specific libraries, tensor data types, data ingestion, visualization, continuum processing) increases the pressure for flexible and effective support for integration of diverse platform capabilities in application workflows. Examples include system software integration packages, mixed-precision arithmetic support, workflow and orchestration capabilities, integration of workflow control with resource management, front-end persistent integration services (e.g. for Spark and TensorFlow or Pytorch). Efficient scaling of training and inference requires a robust infrastructure to sustain the massive execution resource demands, in batch and online (real-time) processing modes, respectively.
- **Efficient integration of virtualisation and containerization approaches** would improve the ease of use, efficiency and resilience of systems. Virtualisation/containerisation must, on the applications side, fulfil their requirements of portability and reproducibility by allowing the definition of encapsulated and customised software stacks, the efficient creation/termination of those software environments on-demand, the seamless and efficient low-latency use of HPC fabrics (e.g. GPU-to-GPU interconnects such as NVLink, InfiniBand across compute nodes), and the secure use of the underlying platform (e.g. rootless, sandboxing). On the infrastructure side, virtualisation/containerisation must feature complete isolation of the applications in a multi-tenant environment, allow agile and

fine-grain dynamic resource provisioning to orchestrate resource sharing in those environments, and integrate HPC (e.g. gang scheduling, affinity, pre-emption, topology-awareness, checkpoint/restore) and Cloud (e.g. autoscaling, elasticity, migration) scheduling and resource management techniques, while providing fault tolerance, energy efficiency, and scalability. To allow arbitration between different users and applications in the current resource management tools, certain features will need to be re-thought in terms of the global workflow: allocation rules, data provisioning and dataflow management policy or engine. This in turn raises new challenges in terms of resiliency, security and reproducibility of simulation.

- **Reproducibility of execution environments** will be a major challenge in the next decade. Integration in applications/workflows of capabilities to capture contextual information and provenance information during application execution with limited scalability/efficiency impact is therefore an important concern. In order to enable this form of reproducibility of execution environments and verifiable provenance, the use of virtualisation will be again essential to provide a portable environment where computation and data processing experiments can be reliably controlled and repeated. A hard challenge for virtualization remains in supporting sharing of high-performance accelerators (esp. GPU devices) and a degree of popular software stacks interoperability across device vendors.
- Research should target mechanisms for **adaptive and dynamic scheduling**, management and use of heterogeneous system components to achieve energy efficiency and resilience, while meeting application performance requirements. HPC-as-a-Service has had an impact on the architecture of management solutions for HPC centres, with an emerging trend towards hybrid infrastructures that include both on-premises and off-premises elements. Supercomputers are increasingly expected to be accessible from the Cloud and be compliant

with the Cloud in terms of system management criteria and practices, while keeping high performance and scalability as major objectives. Significant challenges lie in the coordination of application workflows, resource management and data management cycle, utilising the combination of HPC and Cloud resources. A meta-OS/meta-orchestration approach, which manages both HPC and Cloud orchestrators and seamlessly enables the combined use of HPC and Cloud resources, is essential to reach the required levels of functionality and compliance.

- With an increasing evolution of HPC/HPDA/AI infrastructures towards more dynamic and elastic resource provisioning and management, infrastructure owners/operators are increasingly expected to pay attention to **alignment with development tools and standards**. It is worth stressing that there are still many differences in terms of tools, protocols and philosophy of usage between the HPC and Cloud communities, originating from their different starting points with respect to use cases and application/workflow requirements. This creates a gap, which will have to be bridged for the desired convergence between both disciplines to become a reality, particularly by enabling to a significant degree interoperability, even co-existence, of different usage modes. As technology progresses, applications and computing infrastructures become more complex and heterogeneous. As such, modern scientific applications are reflected into multi-domain (i.e. AI, HPC, HPDA, AI) converged workflows, where different processing stages are executed by a combination of diverse frameworks/stacks (e.g., Spark, MPI, CUDA, SyCL) and infrastructures (Cloud and HPC). Gluing together such diverse ecosystems is not sustainable in the long-term, since even more and more applications benefit from the cross-stack hybridisation; therefore, a more holistic approach is required. This poses significant challenges to the software management layer, with a focus on the Resource and Job Management Software (RJMS), which is responsible for

provisioning the computing, storage and networking resources on one side, and for properly scheduling the execution of jobs on the other hand (orchestration). While Cloud computing relies on a large basis of automation tools to provision resources (incl. machine instances of widely different types) in an elastic manner, Supercomputing systems traditionally rely on batch schedulers where multiple queues allow the management of different execution platforms (e.g., CPUs, CPUs + GPUs, CPUs + FPGAs.) and priorities. Cloud providers by exposing several different machine/instance types.

- Although current-generation batch schedulers support the convergence with Cloud environments, they are limited by coarse-grained models used to express resources and the way these resources are acquired ahead of time and later relinquished. Furthermore, despite their sophisticated heuristic priority functions that allow to guarantee fair access to requested resources by all users, certain limitations still apply. First, these functions are set at the beginning and hardly adapt over time and as workload changes. Second, I/O-awareness is in general not comprehensively considered, leading to performance penalties on modern architectures which embed a growing number of I/O layers (i.e., Burst Buffers, NVRAM). Similar to I/O heterogeneity, access to heterogeneous nodes and accelerators may suffer the rigid resource allocation model of traditional job schedulers, in particular when multiple types of nodes are required by the same job. **The Modular Supercomputing Architecture (MSA)** involves integrating heterogeneous computing resources in a modular way at the system level, each with different hardware and performance characteristics, into a single system [6,7]. Applications and workflows can be run on exactly matching computing resources, thereby improving time and energy to solution. This architecture has been adopted as part of the EuroHPC JU's strategy for exascale computing, aiming to enhance computational power while maintaining energy efficiency.

Moreover, current generation batch schedulers do not provide any workflow-specific mechanism beyond a way to express dependencies among jobs. This can lead to long waiting times incurred by chained jobs. Alternatives can be identified in those strategies that submit large jobs (also referred to as pilot jobs) to the queuing system, acquiring the maximum required resources for the entire runtime. As such, jobs experience a shorter turnaround when compared to chained jobs, but computing resources get higher idle periods. There are challenges to improve RJMS to better support future Exascale machines and hybrid workflows. I/O-aware scheduling is necessary to exploit the full advantages offered by modern I/O and storage hierarchies (which fill the bandwidth gap between the computing nodes and the parallel filesystems). Therefore, improving scheduling algorithms to optimise computing and I/O operations in a coordinated manner are of primary importance (e.g. limiting the number of I/O jobs running concurrently). Furthermore, full utilisation of the available resources can no longer be based solely on simple information provided ahead of time by the users (which tend to overestimate the required resources); the integration of more accurate models is deemed necessary. Machine learning paves the way for extracting the required information in a much more affordable way, allowing the RJMS to rely on a larger knowledge base for making scheduling decisions.

- **Hierarchical scheduling approaches** are seen as means for tackling the scalability problem of applications (higher levels of the hierarchy) while allowing the scheduling algorithm to get advantage of the specificity of the various application domains being part of the workflow at the lower levels. Moreover, hierarchical approaches enable combining resources from systems with quite different capabilities in one unit of work, thus broadening the scope of what a “job” can achieve in a sophisticated execution environment. While some notable examples already exist (e.g., Flux framework for site-customized resource

management), the majority of the currently available RJMS are flat. An additional point can be found in the way workflows are described and presented to the RJMS. Workflows (defined either in a declarative language or via programmatic APIs) are commonly described as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs), in which vertices correspond to the tasks to be executed and the edges are the control/data dependencies among these tasks. Generally, tasks must be mapped to jobs either using the piloting strategy or the chaining strategy described above. However, DAGs are not always sufficient to express the complexity of modern applications that may require features like feedback loops. Moreover, workflow tools are typically assuming that the underlying infrastructure is always available. In fact, even if they can interface with HPC job schedulers, no optimisation of the resource allocation is made to ensure, for instance, that resources needed at the same time by two different steps in the workflow, are allocated together. In general, HPC-oriented workflow management tools require gaining more expressivity in terms of handling different levels of parallelism (DAG level, in-job MPI level, node-level) and mapping them to underlying computational resources in an efficient way (working around limitations of current job schedulers), while keeping the execution level and the resources description and scheduling separated. Moreover, looking at a future perspective, the combination and optimisation of different technological solutions (also already existing) will provide the capability of composing the right set of (virtual) resources needed by a certain workflow, leaving to the resource management system the responsibility to find an optimal mapping with the underlying physical ones. In this perspective, also the capability to support elastic provisioning of physical resources will allow moving beyond the traditional queuing systems, and will set the point for a more interactive integration of HPC and Cloud based ecosystems.

- The **convergence of traditional HPC and HPDA/AI results** has more complex usage modes and workloads as a result. Especially for large-scale HPC systems, this necessitates a modularisation of the runtime environment [6] using standardised interfaces for information exchange between the various components (particularly, PMIx [10, 11]). This will enable the decoupling of key functionalities, e.g., resource management, scheduling and monitoring/accounting. This decoupling will enable the resource management and scheduling infrastructure to be tailored to the requirements of the supercomputing centre, by customising and even replacing, individual components of the system software stack. However, the level of functionality and stability still differs across PMIx releases that focus on different subsets of the standard. More extensive effort toward fuller coverage of functionalities prescribed in the PMIx standard would lead to substantial operational benefits.
- Finally, HPC systems and particularly converged HPC/HPDA/AI systems will need to provide system software support for **advanced security mechanisms** to satisfy increasingly pressing requirements for trustworthy processing of sensitive datasets (with protection measures for code as well as input and output data). This support includes assistance from OS for putting in place several essential security mechanisms enabling isolation and verifiably trusted execution. Particular concerns arise from the need to process sensitive data sets (such as Personally Identifiable Information and data under intellectual property restrictions), necessitating protection against loss of integrity and confidentiality.

Summary of upcoming challenges

The system software stack is a critical component for usability, maintainability and efficiency of a supercomputer. With the diversification of practice and software and hardware components it has become critical to invest in (i) building and integration of “software factories” (i.e. software infrastructure for building and maintaining executable software components of verifiable provenance), and (ii) standard-based federated services for access and deployment of applications.

AI-related challenges

AI users have different practices as compared to traditional HPC users. In turn, such differences have become new constraints in terms of the management and accessibility of software and hardware resources of supercomputers. AI workloads impose the following requirements to HPC environments:

- A ready-to-use AI toolbox designed for deployment on HPC infrastructure, including compatibility with common system software infrastructure services such as workload scheduling via Slurm, delegated SSO (e.g. via Keycloak), and containerized execution. End-users should be able to customize their environments on their own, without increasing the operational support load for system administrators.
- Better productivity of Data Scientists, via collaborative development through sharing of data, models and code, and via support of both a comprehensive scriptable command-line interface (CLI) and an intuitive web portal to facilitate the usage of HPC resources. Further productivity enhancements will come from supporting experiments traceability and information versioning for reproducibility, and with automation of certain error-prone tasks related to AI/ML pipelines (e.g. search for hyperparameters). Ideally, development toolchains, integrated with debugging and

performance analysis tools, should be capable of supporting a very broad spectrum of execution platforms, ranging from the desktop workstation to a high-end supercomputer.

- Efficient investment with a resource sharing model in a multi-tenant environment, to improve return on investment by leveraging resources for multiple end-users, particularly to reduce training speed by leveraging multiple hardware resources in an efficient manner. Co-scheduling is uncommon in classic HPC environments, but the presence of coarse-grained power-hungry accelerators motivates increased attention to (i) finer-grain units of allocation (e.g. a single processor socket associated with one of more GPUs, instead of an entire multi-socket node), and (ii) OS and runtime tuning to mitigate, or at least reduce, performance interference. Recognizing multi-tenancy as a first-tier challenge will become a necessity as long as applications cannot fully utilize one (or a number of) nodes equipped with state-of-the-art accelerators and interconnects.

The requirements listed above have several impacts on (i) organisation of input datasets, models and results of training in HPC storage and in memory; (ii) access control and data security; and (iii) HPC scheduling policy, which must be rethought to better support flexible, malleable and interactive requirements of AI applications.

Optimisation of applications in a development environment very different from supercomputer technologies will require preparation of libraries and basic middleware validation through container repositories that could allow the execution in a supercomputer context.

Software Stack Challenges

This chapter has taken a systems software architect's perspective on engineering HPC systems with more versatility in anticipation of increasingly diverse workloads and complex execution platforms in HPC centres. The following challenges need to be considered:

- Rather than installing and maintaining one single software stack, we propose **shifting the emphasis more on the capacity to build and maintain multiple software stacks** that serve specialized computational and data processing workloads that encompass classic HPC together with Cloud and AI/ML.
- This envisioned shift also points to the **ability to utilize computing nodes based on heterogeneous technologies**, with complex memory/storage system requirements. Moreover, upcoming HPC systems are expected to operate not only as primary execution environments but also as part of workflows that span a compute continuum.
- To achieve high performance, it will remain critical to have in place **pre-tuned “turn-key” software stacks** that can take advantage of specialized hardware components, alongside with associated firmware and operating system support. However, increased versatility in software configurations is required, both for software stacks build from sources and for containerized software services.
- It is critical to deploy and execute only **artifacts of known provenance**, and to provide **strong isolation guarantees even in the anticipated multi-tenant operational** environment. The establishment of regimented software factory processes, as an advanced form of CI/CD flows, is a key safeguard to enable a highly configurable execution environment that is amenable to tractable and auditable modifications. Software factories can potentially generate fully-fledged distributions of both system and application software, ready for deployment. Such distributions can be embedded

in containers to facilitate their sharing by developers across different execution platforms, but also need to be actively maintained by communities.

- Full life-cycle management of software stacks needs to **include hardware simulators/emulators** to be able to prepare software components before the completion of hardware development and availability. The value of this capability has been evidenced recent years with quantum computing devices.

Post-Exascale Vision

The theme of the ISC'24 conference was "Reinventing HPC", with particular emphasis on integrating AI-driven applications and quantum computing. Among other challenges, this broader scope of high-performance computing points to the need to evolve the systems software infrastructure in light of disruption both in workloads and in underlying hardware.

The integration of today's and tomorrow's computing/storage/networking paradigms will be one of the major challenges towards post-Exascale HPC environments, together with the development of efficient software stacks that will efficiently benefit from those emerging solutions while keeping the programming complexity to tractable levels. Regarding potentially disruptive evolution, the combination of quantum computing with AI needs to be considered, as quantum computing has the potential to significantly enhance AI's capabilities [9]. **Such a combination makes seamless integration and interoperability with existing HPC infrastructure even more challenging, particularly towards the convergence of HPC, Cloud, HPDA, and AI/ML infrastructures and their efficient utilization in flexible usage modes.**

Key R&I Recommendations

Globally, integration processes and portability guidelines need to be adopted. It requires hardware-software co-design and co-verification, prototyping, and CI/CD methodologies. Essential software infrastructure components (e.g. EasyBuild, Spack, GitLab, Podman) are already in wide use and have matured significantly, but putting together a robust and scalable CI/CD infrastructure remains an error-prone and maintenance-heavy commitment in the long-term. It is critical to put in place facilities and automation rules, in the form of “software factories”, to enable and enforce modular but real integration of different software and hardware components to effectively and efficiently work together and jointly form the European HPC ecosystem. This requires long-term development strategy and strong coordination among the various actors. It is recommended that focused effort be invested towards raising the TRL level, particularly in support of large codebases with a wide range of software component dependencies and a complex set of configuration settings. Moreover, it is recommended to strive for conformance to the hourglass model [1], and avoid as much as possible overlapping, even incompatible, software stacks that offer silos of dedicated functionality.

Towards this vision of “software factories”, it will be essential to provide communities with:

- continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) resources tailored to HPC and AI/ML software stacks, at both small/medium and large scales;
- turnkey software stacks targeting specific workloads, built continuously;
- adaptations to the underlying heterogeneous hardware architectures;
- performance regression testing and benchmarking;
- standardized libraries and APIs to facilitate ecosystem composability.

Note that initiatives such as Unified Acceleration (UXL), Kokkos, oneAPI and OpenMP demonstrate that software development communities work to address such problems in regard to development environments. At the software stack level, initiatives such as HPSF from Linux Foundation could be an opportunity to federate such efforts. Today such efforts are mainly driven by the US ECP community. Certain software factories initiate CI/CD processes where it could be useful to merge practices in between HPC and the Cloud/Big Data domains. However, even such merging remains a partial solution. Investments must be continued to enhance control of software integration dependencies and conflicts. New, complex applications workflows will need dynamic, live orchestration, which conflicts with current resource management practices on supercomputers. Issues evident in the compute continuum are directly linked with these topics.

Conclusions

Several of the system software domain challenges described in SRA5 [5] remain open, even if the scientific community has since achieved a better understanding of the gap between hardware/software availability and efficient execution of applications. Integration and exploitation of the new computation capabilities must be complemented by strong development operations and integration tools. The system software constitutes the spanning layer in the overall layered architecture of HPC systems, with the increasing prominence of new workloads comprising Big Data and AI/ML processing. The guiding principle (from the Hourglass Theorem [1]) of adopting the weakest spanning layer that can support a specified collection of necessary applications holds true: A minimalist collection of services with well-documented interfaces tends to maximize the variety of underlying services that can support it.

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